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Effects of Audio-Visual-Materials Using Bransford and Steins Model on Interest and Performance in Cell Division among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of audio-visual aids using Bransford and steins model on interest and performance in cell division among senior secondary school students in Zamfara state. Three research questions were raised and three null hypotheses were tested. The study adopted quasi-experimental design involving pre-test and post-test. The total population of the study was 72,577 (42,728 male; 24849 female) senior secondary school students for the 2024/2025 session in all the 189 senior secondary schools in Zamfara state while the target population was twenty-five thousand three hundred and thirty-five (25, 335) SSII biology students. The population of male students were sixteen thousand three hundred and ninety-five (16,395) and the remaining eight thousand nine hundred and forty (8,940) were females. A sample of one hundred and twenty (120) students from an intact class from senior secondary two (SS II) of public schools were selected for this study. The researcher uses audio-visual materials using Bransford and steins model as treatment for the experimental group while control group were exposed to discussion method. The instrument used for data collection was cell division performance test (CDPT) and Cell division interest scale questionnaire (CDISQ). A 30 multiple choice objective type performance test covering the five phases of cell division was used. Reliability co-efficient of 0.82 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson (K-R 21). Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to analyze the hypotheses. The findings revealed that the experimental group performed better than the control group. There was no significant difference in the performance of males and females students. The experimental group retained better than the control group while there was no significant difference in interest in male and female students in the experimental group. It was recommended that teachers should be exposed to the use of audio-visual aids using Bransford and steins model, organize workshops and seminars and symposia on audio-visual aids using Bransford and steins model to assist teachers deliver lessons to enhance learning among students generally.

Keywords: Audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model, Interest, Performance, Cell Division.

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INTRODUCTION

Biology is a field of science that is concerned with study of living things and practical presentations of biological concepts offer by students the opportunity to carry out scientific processes in the laboratory and outside the laboratory, which are far different from theoretical presentations of some of its topics, Omolafe, Ekunola & Omolafe, (2022). It deals with the origin, structure, development, function and distribution of animals and plants in the environment. The teaching of biology is very important because the knowledge of biology helps in improving the quality of life, as it helps to solve many societal problems relating to health, poverty, food shortage, crop production and environmental conservation, Osuafor, Abgail, Chukwuemeka, & Vivian, (2023). Biology is a fundamental topic taught at secondary school level in Nigeria.

However, despite the importance of biology some concepts pose difficult for students particularly when discussing ideas that are abstract or cannot be fully comprehended by learners for the first time, these courses include cell, microbiology, genetics, medicine, zoology, botany, evolution, ecology and cell division among many others, Moriki, Faruk & Tambuwal, (2023). Researchers had also use traditional teaching methods to teach cell division concept which often focus on role memorization and passive learning.

This traditional strategy may not adequately engage students or promote deep understanding of cell division concepts among students, failure rate still persist. Poor performance among senior secondary school students could be attributed to students' lack of interest in the subject or concept, teacher's insufficient background knowledge, lack of practical experience and poor method of instruction. Hence, there is a need to explore an alternative teaching strategies that can improve students' performance and interest in cell division concept.

Cell division is the process by which a parent cell divides in to two daughter cells. According to (Opeyemi, Bolanle, Arinde, Omowumi & Sefinat, 2022) cell division process is a part of the cell cycle. Scientists discovered by the end of the nineteenth century that two types of nuclear division occur in the cell of living organisms. These two types of cell division are necessary if the organisms are to reproduce in life, they are mitosis and meiosis. Mitosis in cell: This a type of cell division that leads to the formation of new cells. It is known that multicellular organisms grow from their original single cell to form cells of the adult as a result of repeated cell divisions Gulen, (2019). Mitosis has five distinct phases: (1) Interphase (2) Prophase (3) Metaphase (4) Anaphase and (5) Telophase.

Meiosis in cell: Is a type of nuclear division in which the chromosome number is halved that is, from the diploid number ($2n$) to haploid number (n). Gulen, (2019). The process that occurs in meiosis are continuous however for convenience it is divided into four phases: (1) Prophase I (2) Metaphase I (3) Anaphase I and (4) Telophase I. Mitosis and meiosis are abstract concept in biology that students found it very difficult to understand, so it requires a vivid explanation more especially to the students in science with the use of audio-visual aids.

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Audio-visual aids is referred to as a multi-sensory interactive application or presentation that uses a variety of digital media types to communicate message or information to an audience, including text, pictures, sound, and video Allwell, Olajumoke & Kayode (2022), As a result, when words are supplemented by pictures and animations, ideas are simpler to convey and understand, giving the learning experience a whole new level since ten percent (10%) of what individual hear and read remembered, twenty percent (20%) of what they see remembered, and eighty percent (80%) of what they see and do is remembered Omolefe, Ekunola & Omolafe (2022). Teaching aids such as the audio-visuals yield more benefits in teaching/learning processes especially when used with relevant teaching models like the bransford and steins model.

Bransford and steins model is an instructional model that help both the teacher and the learner to solve learning difficulties by identifying the learning difficulties. (Ibrahim, Maruta, Bolaji, Musa & Ibrahim, 2022) define bransford and steins model refers to a teaching model which emphasizes five components of thinking that are applicable to wide variety of situations. These include: (i) identifying a problem; (ii) defining and representing the problem with precision; (iii) exploring possible strategies; (iv) acting on these strategies; and (v) looking at the effect. Note that the first letters of each of these components is found in the word IDEAL. The integration of audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model in education has long been recognized as a crucial factor in enhancing the learning experience, especially in subjects that require a deep understanding of complex concepts, such as cell division, Biology is essential in many aspects of life and plays a significant part in sciences, and is also a subject that is used in measuring student's academic performance.

Academic performance should be considered to be a multifaceted construct that comprises different domains of learning. A number of science educators such as Sabo, Musa, Ahmad & Yahuza, (2021) have reported the downward trend in the performance of Nigerian students in science subjects at the senior secondary school certificate examination attributed to students' poor performance in biology at public examinations. The research seeks to determine whether these tools can enhance students' engagement with the subject matter and improve their academic outcomes, thereby contributing to the broader field of understanding the concept of cell division and increase the students' interest.

Interest in the context of education connotes the inclination of students towards a particular subject in which he or she is easily able to connect without any difficulty. Interest is both a psychological state of attention and effect toward a particular object or topic, and an enduring predisposition to reengage over time Tron, L.C, (2021). Interest deals with engaging and re-engaging with the same ideas, objects, or events. It could rightly be said that as students' interests increase, they will have significant improvement in their overall academic performance without considering their gender.

Gender effect is an issue of concern in this research, and the researcher mainly to identify male and female performance in a given study. According to UNESCO, (2024) gender in education is very important because gender is a fundamental component of our society.

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Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognized importance of biology as a science subject, empirical studies such as those of Adegboye, Ganiyu & Issac, (2017) have shown that students still perform poorly in biology at senior secondary school certificate examination. The registrar and the CEO of the national examinations council (NECO) Professor Danlami Ibrahim Wushishi revealed that Zamfara state among other states mentioned have lowest performance in the 2024 senior secondary school examination (SSCE) (Daily Trust E-Paper, 2024).

Objectives of the Study

Objectives of the study are to:

- i. Investigate the effect of audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model on students' interest in cell division
- ii. determine the effect of audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model on students' academic performance in cell division.
- iii. Compare the performance of male and female students taught with audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model in cell division.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated for answering:

- i. Is there any difference in the mean score of students' interest when taught cell division concept with audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model and those taught using traditional lecture method?
- ii. Is there any differences in the mean scores of students taught cell division concept with audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model and those taught using traditional lecture method?.
- iii. Is there any significant difference in performance between male and female students taught with audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model in cell division?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses is formulated and tested at $p < 0.05$ significant levels.

Ho₁. There is no significant differences in students' mean interest score in cell division when taught with audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model and those taught with traditional teaching method.

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Ho₂. There is no significant differences in the mean performance score between students taught cell division with audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model and compare to those taught with traditional lecture method.

Ho₃. There is no significant differences in the academic performance of male and female students taught with audio-visual Materials using Bransford and steins model.

Research Methodology

The study used quasi-experimental control design involving pre-test and post-test. The total population of the study was 72,577 (42,728 male; 24849 female) senior secondary school students for the 2024/2025 session in all the 189 senior secondary schools in Zamfara state while the target population was twenty-five thousand three hundred and thirty-five (25, 335) SSII biology students. The population of male students were sixteen thousand three hundred and ninety-five (16,395) and the remaining eight thousand nine hundred and forty (8,940) were females. A sample of one hundred and twenty (120) students from an intact class from senior secondary two (SS II) of public schools were selected for this study. The study involves experimental group and a control group consisting of both males and female subjects of an intact class.

A pretest was administered to the group using cell performance test (CDPT) before treatment to determine the equivalence of the students and the control group were taught using discussion method. The procedure of sample and sampling technique was done by stratifying the educational zones into four strata and that is Kaura Namoda zone, Talata mafara zone, Anka zone, and Gusau zone after stratifying this zones each zone was selected using simple random techniques by balloting thereby picking one local government from each of the educational zone making it four local government which was subjected to ANOVA the result from the ANOVA was subjected to scheffe's test, the result of the scheffe's test simple random sampling was used to assign the group into experimental and control group accordingly. Simple random sampling technique was used to assign students as males and females. Two instruments was used for this study: Cell Division Performance Test (CDPT), Cell division interest scale questionnaire (CDISQ).

The research instruments was validated by experts from the departments of science education, educational foundations (measurement and evaluation) and biological sciences Federal University Gusau. The CDPT adopted from standardized WAEC (SSCE) question papers (2019-2024). The CDPT contained 30 objective questions with 4 responses. The result of the test was analyzed to establish the reliability coefficients using the Pearson product moment coefficient (PPMC) which yielded a coefficient of 0.82. The data were collected through the procedure of pretest, treatment and posttest administration of the CDPT. Mean and Standard Deviation were used in answering the research questions and t-test was used in testing the null hypotheses at $p < 0.05$ significant level.

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Presentation of Results

Before the administration of the treatment, a pretest was administered to the two groups of students (experimental and Control) to determine the entry knowledge of the students with regards to the content to be learnt (Cell division).

Table 1 t-test analysis of pretest scores of experimental and control Groups.

Variable	N	df	\bar{x}	SD
Experimental Group	58	118	35.250	6.242
Control group	62		36.166	7.035

Table 1 Revealed that the mean score of the experimental and control groups before the treatment did not vary significantly. The Experimental Group has a mean score of 35.250 while the control group has a mean score of 36.166 and marginal mean score 1.084 which is not significant at 0.05 alpha level of significance. Hence the two groups of students were thus considered suitable for the research study based on the aforementioned marginal difference in the mean scores.

Posttest Results

Test of Hypotheses

This presents the results collated after the administration of the treatment to the group with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model strategy and the control group with discussion method.

Ho₁. There is no significant differences in students' mean interest score in cell division when taught with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model and those taught with traditional teaching method.

Table 2 Analysis of Covariance of Posttest Scores of Experimental and Control Group taught with CDPT and discussion method respectively.

Variable	N	df	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal	sign(2-tailed)
Experimental Group	58	118	38.316	2.432	0.078	0.012
Control Group	62		36.966	3.319		

Significant at $p < 0.05$ level

Table 2 indicates that among the two groups, the audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model led instructional group has the highest mean score of 38.316 on interest compared to 36.966 of the

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control group. This suggests that the audio-visual aids using branford and steins model led instructional group had better opportunities of interest in what was learnt compared to the discussion group. The t-value calculated of 0.078, SD = 2.432 and 3.319 is significant at 0.12 less than 0.05 alpha level. Therefore hypothesis one was rejected, that is, there is significant difference between the mean interest scores of students taught cell division with audio-visual aids using branford and steins model and those taught by discussion method.

Ho₂. There is no significant differences in the mean performance score between students taught cell division with audio-visual aids using branford and steins model and compare to those taught with traditional lecture method.

Table 3. Analysis of Covariance of Posttest mean performance scores of experimental and control groups.

Variable	N	df	x	SD	t-cal	sign.(2-tailed)
Experimental Group	58		41.166	2.656		
Control Group	62	118	38.233	3.290	5.373	0.00

Significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 3 revealed that the experimental group taught the concept of cell division with audio-visual aids using branford and steins model did better than the control group taught using discussion method. The experimental group has higher mean score of 41.166 on the posttest performance score compared to 38.233 of the control group. This shows that the experimental group had better understand of the concept cell division through audio-visual aids using branford and steins model than the students in the control group and with a marginal difference of 2.933 which is significant. However, the test of hypothesis revealed that the t-value calculated 5.373 is significant at 0.000 less than 0.05 alpha level, $df = 188$, $SD = 2.656$ and 3.290 respectively. Hence hypothesis two was rejected an the alternative upheld, that is, there is significant difference between the performance of students taught cell division through audio-visual aids using branford and steins model against those taught using discussion method.

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H₀₃. There is no significant differences in the academic performance of male and female students taught with audio-visual Materials using bransford and steins model.

Table 4 Analysis of Covariance of Posttest Scores of the Experimental Male and Female Taught cell division with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model.

Variables	N	df	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal	sign(2 tailed)
Experimental Males	30		35.583	3.271		
Experimental Females	30	58	35.833	3.387	.658	.512NS

Not significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 4 shows that the mean scores of the male students and female students in the experimental group taught cell division with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model did not differ significantly (35.583 and 35.833). The females in the experimental group had a marginal mean difference in the posttest of 0.250 over the males in the same group. The result from the test of hypothesis three revealed that the $t\text{-cal} = .658$, $df = 58$, $SD = 3.271$ and 3.387 is not significant at ($p > .512$). Therefore, hypothesis three not rejected. That is there is no significant difference between the performance of male and female students taught cell division via audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model.

Findings

The findings of this study are follows:-

- i. There was difference between in the mean academic performance scores of the students taught cell division with audio-visual using bransford and steins model and those taught using the discussion method.
- ii. There was difference in the mean academic performance of students taught with audio-visual Materials using bransford and steins model between male and female students, but the difference was statistically not significant.

Discussion

The findings of the study disclosed that there was difference between the mean score of performance of the students taught cell division with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model and those taught with discussion method. This was indicated by the groups' mean difference and the result of the one-way ANCOVA analysis. This implies that teaching students with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model help students learn and comprehend even the difficult part of cell division more easily than using discussion method.

Regarding to gender and performance, the findings revealed also that there was difference in the mean performance in cell division between male and female exposed to audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model in favour of the females but the difference was statistically not significant. This was

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shown by the mean difference in the performance and the result of the one-way ANCOVA on the performance scores of the male and female students taught with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model. The strategy is gender friendly and suitable for both male and female students' with verifying intellectual abilities, learning styles and interest as it gives room for all students to actively participate in the lesson irrespective of their gender.

Conclusion

The following conclusions are made based on the findings of this study. The results of this study provided empirical evidence that the use of audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model enhanced students' performance and interest in cell division more than the discussion method.

Male and female students taught cell division with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model perform better than male and female students taught cell division with discussion method. There was no significant difference between the mean performance scores of males and females taught cell division with audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model. Gender has no significant influence on performance and interest between the both sexes.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:-

- i. Since the use of audio-visual Materials using bransford and steins model enhances performance and interest in cell division, biology teachers should be encouraged to use it as a strategy to employ in the classroom.
- ii. Audio-visual Materials need to be made more available in government schools at all levels so that learners can access it and use it without stress.
- iii. Seminar and Workshops should be organized for teachers, authors and curriculum planners on how to use audio-visual Materials using bransford and steins model as this will go a long way in helping the learners to understand abstract concept easily.

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